

DAMAGE TO CARBON FIBRES DURING RADIAL BRAIDING

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Keywords: Radial Braiding, Carbon Fibre, Tow Damage

ABSTRACT

Radial braiding enables the rapid manufacture of composite fabric preforms via automation. However, braided textile composites generally have lower mechanical properties than prepreg or woven laminates. This has hindered their use in aircraft structures. We have investigated the effects of the radial braiding process on the damage, shape, tensile strength and stiffness of carbon fibre tows. The tensile properties of carbon fibre tows were measured after bobbin winding and every key stage of the radial braiding process. These properties did not change significantly during braiding, although a small percentage of fibres were broken. Acoustic emission monitoring during tensile testing revealed that the onset of fibre damages occurred as early as the bobbin winding stage. In addition, significant changes occurred to the tow shape during braiding. Our results show that damage to carbon fibre tows during radial braiding is limited to a small number of fibre filaments and this does not affect the bulk mechanical properties of the tows.

1 INTRODUCTION

Radial braiding is used to manufacture fabrics for composite materials in automobiles, jet engine casings, sports goods and other products. Braiding enables the manufacture of fabric preforms with varying cross-sections, reduces material wastage, and increases production rate through automation of the fabrication process. In addition, unlike traditional woven fabrics in which tows only intersect orthogonally, tows in braids interlace at angles ranging between 15° to 75° [1]. This flexibility in tow angle permits highly efficient composite structures to be fabricated.

Despite these advantages, the use of braided composites is limited in aircraft structures compared to tape and woven laminates. This is partly due to the high cost of qualifying new structural materials for commercial aircraft. More importantly, braided composites generally have lower in-plane mechanical properties than tape laminates [2]. The reasons for the lower properties include fibre crimp [2, 3] and fibre damage [4, 5] caused by the braiding process. Falzon and Herszberg [4] report that braiding reduced the tensile properties of carbon fibre tows by as much as 20%. However, how damage occurs to carbon fibres during each stage of the braiding process has not been determined. Understanding how tow damage occurs at each stage of braiding will open up opportunities to modify the process to minimise fibre damage. This can lead ultimately to improvements in the mechanical properties of braided composites.

In this work, we have investigated the damage that occurs to carbon tows during the radial braiding process in the fabrication of braided fabrics. The changes to the tensile properties of carbon tows as they progress through the entire radial braiding process from bobbin winding to the final braid fabric was investigated. In addition, we observed changes to the shape of carbon tows as they process through the braided process.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Continuous Toho Tenax HTS40, 12K (800 tex) carbon tows were used in this study to assess the effects of radial braiding on carbon fibre damage. The carbon tows were wound onto bobbins using a semi-automatic bobbin winder supplied by Herzog. The bobbins were loaded onto a 48 carrier Herzog radial braiding machine. A Kuka robot fed a mandrel through the braiding machine at a constant speed during braiding. The equipment used is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: (a) Semi-automatic bobbin winder and (b) Radial braiding machine and robot.

The key steps involved in producing a braided fabric are shown in Figure 2. Tows are first wound onto bobbins. The bobbins are loaded onto carriers on the braiding machine. The tows are then manually threaded through the eyelets on individual carriers. Braid sleeves, flat sheets, overbraids and complex shape preforms can then be produced.

Figure 2: Key steps involved in producing a braid.

The radial braiding process itself consists of three core stages. In sequential order, the stages involve (i) bending of the tows around the baffle as they are drawn from the carrier bobbins under tension, (ii) travel of the tows from the carrier to the braid ring while being twisted, and (iii) bending of the tows over the braid ring and travel to the mandrel where the braided fabric is formed.

Carbon tows were extracted carefully by hand from bobbins and several locations in the braiding process to determine their mechanical properties and shape (see Fig. 3). Where necessary, the braiding process was paused to allow the tows to be removed. The first location (A) is positioned between the carriers and the braid ring. The second location (B) is after the braid ring. The third location (C) is on the braid fabric and corresponds to the end of the braiding process. Tows were taken from locations A and C for tensile testing and acoustic emission monitoring at room temperature ($20 \pm 5^\circ\text{C}$). During tensile testing, the dry tow was attached to a specially designed fixture and loaded at an extension rate of 2 mm/minute using an Instron 50 kN test machine. During testing, breakages to the fibre were monitored using acoustic emission analysis. A minimum of 20 tows from each position were tensile tested to determine the average stiffness and failure stress values, and the amount of scatter. From locations A, B and C, the tows were examined with high resolution X-ray computed tomography (CT) using a GE Phoenix v/tome/xs unit with a micro-focus X-ray tube operated at a voltage ranging between 20-50 kV and current of 200-250 μA . In addition, tensile tests and X-ray CT examination of the tows in their original as-received condition was performed to establish the baseline.

Figure 3: Schematic showing the major stages of radial braiding. A, B and C are the locations where tows were taken for X-ray CT examination and/or tensile testing. Location A is positioned between the carriers and the braid ring, location B is positioned after the braid ring while location C is on the braid, which corresponds to the end of the braiding process.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 4 is a box plot showing the variation of tensile failure stress and bulk modulus of the tows through radial braiding. The centre line is the median, the upper and lower boundaries of the box are the first and third quartiles, and the upper and lower horizontal bars represent the maximum and minimum values. Small variations exist in the median stiffness and failure stress values between the stages, however, there is no systematic trend nor are the differences statistically significant.

An example load versus crosshead displacement curve recorded during tensile testing of a tow is shown in Figure 5. The curve is overlaid with the cumulative acoustic emission events (total hits) for the same test (red dotted line in Figure 5). High resolution photographs of the tow taken at different times during the test are also shown. Figure 5 can be separated into three regions: (1) slack in the tow is removed as load is applied, (2) linear elastic region and (3) loss of linearity due to fibre breakages ultimately causing complete rupture of the tow. Curves of similar shapes were recorded for tows taken at any stage of the braiding process.

Figure 4: Variation of (a) failure stress and (b) bulk stiffness of the dry carbon tows through bobbin winding and radial braiding.

Figure 5: Typical load versus crosshead displacement curve of a tow overlaid with the cumulative acoustic emission hits with (a) showing initial slack in the tow, (b) tow straightening under load, (c) and (d) showing a small number of filaments breaking in the linear elastic region of the curve, (e) showing an instantaneous burst of fibre breakage events accompanying the loss of linearity in the load versus displacement curve and (f) showing the final state of the tow after the test.

Acoustic emission monitoring performed during tensile testing revealed that the onset of fibre breakages occurred at slightly lower stresses for tows from bobbins and at significantly lower stresses for braided tows, as shown in Figure 6. The onset of fibre breakages was defined arbitrarily as the value of failure stress at which the first five percent of the acoustic events have occurred. This is expressed as a percentage of the final failure stress of the tow. Data from five acoustics recordings were used to plot each bar in Figure 6. The failure stress to initiate fibre breakages shows a general downward trend as the tow progresses along the braiding process. However, the changes are not statistically significant until the tow reaches the very end of the braiding process (i.e. location C). The earlier onset of fibre breakages also did not affect the bulk stiffness and failure stress of the tows. Hence, it can be said that the damage to carbon fibre tows during radial braiding is limited to a small number of filaments.

Figure 6: Variation in the onset of fibre breakages expressed as a percentage of the failure stress of the tow, where onset is defined as the stress at which five percent of the acoustic events have taken place.

Visual observations confirm that the limited amount of fibre damage was caused by (i) tow/machinery abrasion over bobbin winder components and the carrier, (ii) tow twist as the tows moved from the carriers to the braid ring and (iii) the tows' crisscrossing actions over themselves and the braid ring. As seen in Figure 7, the path of the tows during radial braiding is complex. The tows curve, slide and bend sharply over a short distance in the carrier. In addition, the twisting action as tows travel from the carriers to the braid ring damages the tow. The twist is induced by the sinusoidal movement of carriers during braiding. This twisting action was seen to cause tows to separate, as shown in Figure 8(a). The separation of tows produced stray filaments that were prone to entanglement with adjacent tows. In cases of severe filament/tow entanglement, the braiding operation had to be stopped completely. From bobbin winding through to the end of the braiding process, it was observed that the most amount of filament breakages occurred as the tows crisscrossed and passed over the braid ring. Broken filaments were seen to accumulate in the vicinity of the ring after several braiding operations, as shown in Figure 8 (b).

Figure 7: Photographs showing (a) the path of a tow as it passes over a carrier and (b) tows twisting as they pass from the carriers to the braid ring.

Figure 8: Photographs showing tows crisscrossing and bending as they pass over the braid ring, with a small number of broken filaments visible in both (a) and (b).

The shape of the tows changed progressively during the braiding process, as shown by the X-ray CT images in Figure 9. The tows in the original (as-received) condition were untwisted and flat, with the fibres evenly distributed (Fig. 9a). During the braiding process the tows became progressively more twisted and circular in cross section, with the greatest change occurring when they passed over the braid ring (Fig. 9d). The internal arrangement of the fibres also changed, with the tows separating into discrete and randomly-sized fibre bundles with void space in between. The separation of fibre filaments in the tow suggests that sizing agent, which “bind” filaments together and protect them during processing, may have been affected and this is currently under investigation.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A systematic study on damage to carbon fibre tows during radial braiding has been conducted, including a comprehensive assessment into the effect of the actions of braiding on the mechanical properties and physical form of the carbon tows. The strength and stiffness of the tows did not change significantly during braiding. However, individual filaments were damaged as early as the bobbin winding stage and the braiding actions caused the tow to separate into randomly sized and distributed bundles. It is believed that the geometric changes to the tow shape may contribute to a reduction in the mechanical properties of braided laminates. This is also currently under investigation.

Figure 9: Longitudinal and cross-sectional CT images showing the progressive change in the shape of the carbon tows: (a) as-received tows, (b) tows from bobbins, (c) tows from Location A, (d) tows from Location B and (e) tows from Location C.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to express their gratitude to Sebastian Naseli, technical staff from RMIT's Advance Manufacturing Department, for his assistance during braid manufacturing and contributions to photography.

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